

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D8.7 COVINFORM COVID-19 Knowledge Repository

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101016247.

Project

Acronym	COVINFORM
Title	Coronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation dynamics Research and Modelling
Coordinator	SYNYO GmbH
Reference	101016247
Type	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Programme	HORIZON 2020
Topic	SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2C Behavioural, social and economic impacts of the outbreak response
Start	01 November 2020
Duration	36 months
Website	https://covinform.eu
Consortium	<p>SYNYO GmbH (SYNYO), Austria</p> <p>Magen David Adom in Israel (MDA), Israel</p> <p>Samur Proteccion Civil (SAMUR), Spain</p> <p>Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (UCSC), Italy</p> <p>SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH (SINUS), Germany</p> <p>Trilateral Research LTD (TRI UK), UK</p> <p>Trilateral Research LTD (TRI IE), Ireland</p> <p>Kentro Meleton Asfaleias – Center for Security Studies (KEMEA), Greece</p> <p>Factor Social Consultoria em Psicossociologia e Ambiente LDA (FS), Portugal</p> <p>Austrian Red Cross (AUTRC), Austria</p> <p>Media Diversity Institute (MDI), UK</p> <p>Societatea Națională de Cruce Rosie Din România – Romanian Red Cross (SNCRR), Romania</p> <p>University of Antwerp (UANTWERPEN), Belgium</p> <p>Sapienza University of Rome (SAPIENZA), Italy</p> <p>University Rey Juan Carlos (URJC), Spain</p> <p>Swansea University (SU), UK</p> <p>Gotenborg University (UGOT), Sweden</p>

Acknowledgement: This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101016247.

Disclaimer: The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the authors, and in no way represents the view of the European Commission or its services.

Deliverable

Number	D8.7
Title	COVINFORM COVID-19 Knowledge Repository
Lead beneficiary	TRI
Work package	WP8
Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Nature	Other (O)
Due date	31.10.2023
Submission date	27.10.2023
Authors	Zainab Mehdi, TRI
Contributors	Niamh Aspell, TRI
Reviewers	Elena Ambrosetti, SAPIENZA

Document history

Version	Date	Comments
0.1	22.09.2023	Internal review
0.2	28.09.2023	Internal feedback received
0.3	10.10.2023	Second internal review
0.4	12.10.2023	Internal review with updates
0.5	18.10.2023	Internal feedback addressed and sent for external review
0.6	24.10.2023	External review received
0.6	26.10.2023	Deliverable sent to PO

Executive Summary

The focus of D8.7 COVINFORM COVID-19 Knowledge Repository is to report the creation of the COVINFORM knowledge repository, which is an online database that “helps capture, store, and categorize knowledge-based information.”¹ The COVID-19 pandemic required immediate and shared efforts by the research community, policy makers and authorities to rapidly investigate the virus, its attributes and the response measures to overcome the pandemic with as limited impact as possible. This resulted in an influx of knowledge sharing via publications, events, and data sharing. The objective of creating a knowledge repository is not only to maintain COVID-19-related information during the pandemic, but also to ensure the quality of information and ease of accessibility for the public. The knowledge repository resources include COVID-19-related information in various domains such as Government, Economy, Health, Communities, Communication, Science and Technology, Education, Gender, Climate, Law, Poverty, Industry and Labour, and Healthcare Services. In addition, the knowledge repository brings together a selection of resources acknowledged and evaluated as part of Work Packages (WPs) 2-7 and indexes valuable COVID-19 resources that are relevant for government and public health representatives, CSOs, NGOs, policymakers, and citizens. The resources include Funding Opportunities, Initiatives, Projects, Reports, Policy briefs, Conference papers, Briefs, Blogs, E-books/handbooks, and Data sources. COVINFORM deliverables and scientific literature have also been considered. The repository has been developed and presented (during the project) in the cloud, leveraging high-speed and secure data storage facilities using the Amazon Simple Storage Service (AWS S3). The knowledge repository has been integrated into the WP2 dashboard since M20 of the COVINFORM project via a multifunctional search engine. Furthermore, the COVINFORM website also contains a repository of relevant sources pertaining to COVID-19-related information. Finally, the COVINFORM consortium created Zenodo accounts. To date, the consortium has been uploading relevant documents to the platform, which is an open-source repository. Uploads will only take place until the project has developed and finalised the repository on 31 October 2023.

1 Sabdani, J. (2023). Retrieved from <https://knowmax.ai/blog/knowledge-repository-software/>

Contents

Executive Summary	4
1 Introduction.....	7
2 Methodology	8
2.1 Creating the Knowledge Repository	8
3 Overview of the Knowledge Repository.....	9
3.1 WP2 Dashboard	9
3.2 COVINFORM website	10
3.3 Zenodo	10
4 Licensing	11
5 Conclusion	12

Figures

Figure 1. Presentation of the knowledge repository integrated into the WP2 dashboard.....9

Figure 2. COVINFORM website knowledge repository.....10

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
WPs	Work Packages
AWS S3	Amazon Simple Storage Service or Amazon S3
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation

1 Introduction

This report concerns the creation of a knowledge repository for the COVINFORM project. The fundamental goal of a knowledge repository is to “capture knowledge by taking documents that have knowledge embedded in them and to store them in a repository to which all authorised employees have access.”² In the case of COVINFORM, the end users are Public Health Representatives, CSOs, NGOs, Policymakers, and Citizens. This deliverable, otherwise known as D8.7 COVINFORM COVID-19 Knowledge Repository, collated a variety of the resources recognised and assessed as part of WPs 2-7 and built a repository of beneficial COVID-19 resources. Once the COVINFORM project comes to an end on 31 October 2023, the repository will be made available via the COVINFORM project’s WP2 dashboard. The resources uploaded will come in the form of Funding Opportunities, Initiatives, Projects, Reports, Policy Papers, Briefs, Conference Papers, Blogs, eBook/Handbook, Data sources, Events. In addition to external resources, the COVINFORM COVID-19 knowledge repository comprises the project’s public deliverables. Relevant labels (e.g., geographic location covered, the topic, etc.) have been attached to the different resources so that they can be searched easily. The resources have been uploaded to an open-source repository named Zenodo. Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN, otherwise known as the European Organization for Nuclear Research. Besides the WP2 dashboard and Zenodo, the project’s COVINFORM website also comprises a knowledge repository.

This deliverable will be divided into four different chapters. Chapter 2 will cover the methodology of the COVID-19 knowledge repository. This chapter will specifically focus on the criteria to be considered for the resources to be included. Then, Chapter 3 will provide an overview of the knowledge repository, by specifically looking at how the repository has been integrated into the WP2 dashboard, the creation of a repository available on the COVINFORM website, and the upload of resources via Zenodo, which the COVINFORM consortium have added to the project until the final repository is ready by 31 October 2023. Chapter 4 provides a brief overview of the licences used for the uploaded content, the process and reasoning there. Finally, Chapter 5 will provide a conclusion of the deliverable.

² <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/computer-science/knowledge-repository#:~:text=The%20underlying%20goal%20is%20to,all%20authorised%20employees%20have%20access>

2 Methodology

This section discusses the criteria for selecting the most appropriate resources to be uploaded onto the Knowledge Repository. To learn more about the technical methods of the dashboard, please refer to *D2.3 Technical Report*, *D2.4 Cloud-based interactive dashboard for displaying geospatial layers*, and *D2.7 Technical Report and Database*.

2.1 Creating the Knowledge Repository

A specific criterion was set for selecting the most appropriate outputs that should be uploaded to the knowledge repository. The outputs the COVINFORM consortium chose to focus on are Funding Opportunities, Initiatives, Projects, Reports, Policy Papers, Briefs, Conference Papers, Blogs, eBook/Handbook, Data sources, Events. Furthermore, the consortium agreed to upload COVINFORM public deliverables and scientific literature either cited in the COVINFORM deliverables or externally. For the latter, only key publications were considered and the COVINFORM consortium defined key publications as by high Impact Factor journals, reports from governing agencies, institutions, and highly cited papers. As for reports from governing agencies, institutions, the consortium chose to include resources from the European Parliament, European Council, Council of the European Union, European Commission, Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU), European Central Bank (ECB), European Economic and Social Committee, WHO, UN. Regarding highly cited papers, an agreement was made to upload papers with >300 citations. The overall themes covered include Government, Economy, Health, Nutrition and Population, Communities, Communication, Science and Technology, Education, Gender, Climate, Law, Poverty, Industry and Labour, Trade, and Healthcare Services.

The COVINFORM deliverables that have been uploaded to the Knowledge Repository are limited to public deliverables. The deliverables which are not public yet will be uploaded after the project comes to an end on 31 October 2023. The database will be active for at least one year after the project ends. Therefore, access to the Knowledge Repository via the dashboard will be guaranteed for at least that time. Nevertheless, the Knowledge Repository will be available via the COVINFORM website and will be stored permanently on Zenodo.

3 Overview of the Knowledge Repository

This section provides an overview of the results of the various components comprising the knowledge repository created for the COVINFORM project. The overview focuses on the repository uploaded on the COVINFORM website, and the repository integrated into the COVINFORM project's WP2 dashboard. The overview also touches on the integration of the Knowledge Repository into Zenodo, intended as a temporary storage database until the completion of the repository integration into the WP2 dashboard on 31 October 2023.

3.1 WP2 Dashboard

The knowledge repository has been integrated into the COVINFORM [project's dashboard](#) as part of WP2. As mentioned in D2.4 Cloud-based interactive dashboard for displaying geospatial layers, the data catalogue of unstructured data ('Knowledge Repository') the COVINFORM project has compiled is diverse both in content and in the type of data it signifies. At present, the range of different datasets have been indexed. The task of indexing depended on categorising the datasets into numerous different categories. There are four fields indexed for each item: Name, URL, Category, and Authors (either persons or organisations). This index is hosted using the Trilateral Research [STRIAD](#) AWS S3, which can then be searched using the STRIAD search engine outlined in [Section 3.2](#), as well as downloaded directly, if necessary, into a CSV format.

With this in mind, the unstructured data collected by the COVINFORM project is in text (PDF) format, comprising both project reports and scientific literature. As these PDFs are hosted on third-party sites, the most effective way of providing access to this data via the dashboard is by the formatted results being displayed correctly on the dashboard, with the item name, authors, and a link to where the data is hosted (if available) displayed.

Browse a collection of COVID-19 related resources created or recommended by the COVINFORM project (i)

Enter texts to search by Keywords

Search the COVINFORM Knowledge Repository

Select to search either by Keywords, Document Name or Authors.

Keywords

Select which document type of unstructured data to search

All Document Types

All Years

All Topics

Bi-monthly report 01 – COVID-19 Vaccines: History and Facts
By Elena Ambrosetti, Marina Zannella, Diotima Bertel, Su Anson, Alberto Hernández Tejedor
<https://www.covinform.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/39/2021/01/COVINFORM-Bi-Monthly-Report-01-A4-1.0.pdf>

Bi-monthly report 02 – COVID-19 vaccination campaign in COVINFORM countries: infographics & best practices
By Elena Ambrosetti, Marina Zannella, Itamar Laist, Chaim Rafalowski
<https://www.covinform.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/39/2021/03/COVINFORM-Brochure-A4-Bi-Monthly-Report-2.pdf>

Bi-monthly report 03 – A Glimpse of the Lessons Learned During the COVID-19 Pandemic

Figure 1 Presentation of the knowledge repository integrated into the WP2 dashboard

3.2 COVINFORM website

The [COVINFORM website](#) is managed by COVINFORM partner SYNYO (Austria). The website includes a repository focusing on:

1. Communication & Misinformation. This [page](#) includes data on COVINFORM outputs, literature, initiatives, projects, events, and funding opportunities.
2. Models & Data Sources. This [page](#) includes data on models and data sets, literature, and initiatives.
3. Events. This [page](#) includes data on past and upcoming events.

Figure 2 COVINFORM website knowledge repository

3.3 Zenodo

The COVINFORM Consortium created Zenodo accounts. To date, the Consortium have been uploading relevant documents to the platform, which is an open-source repository. Uploads will only take place until the project has developed and finalised the repository on 31 October 2023.

4 Licensing

For this deliverable, the COVINFORM consortium considered Creative Commons ('CC') Licences. 'CC' licenses enable copyright holders to grant consent to others to copy or alter their work in ways that would otherwise breach copyright law. There are several different 'CC' licenses,³ and for the COVINFORM knowledge repository, it was decided that the most applicable license to use would be Attribution: CC BY. Adding to this, the scientific literature and public deliverables uploaded to Zenodo were all affiliated with Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0). This attribution allows for maximum dissemination and use of licensed materials.⁴ Further information on 'CC' licensing can be accessed [here](#).

³ About CC licenses. (2023). Retrieved from <https://creativecommons.org/about/ccllicenses/>

5 Conclusion

This deliverable has presented the COVINFORM project's knowledge repository built for the purpose of informing the research community about the vast number of relevant and useful information relating to the COVID-19 pandemic. The consortium have created a knowledge repository that comprises external scientific literature focusing on the COVID-19 pandemic and the project's public deliverables. In addition, this deliverable has touched on the integration of the knowledge repository into the COVINFORM project's WP2 dashboard and creation of a separate repository uploaded on the COVINFORM website. Furthermore, the deliverable has also touched on the upload of documents on Zenodo. After this date, the repository can be accessed by the public temporarily and will only be publicly available for at least one year after the project comes to an end on 31 October 2023. After this date, the repository can no longer be accessed.